

CiviMatics: Mathematical modelling meets civic education

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While mathematical modelling generally has an important position in mathematics education, discussions and approaches about normative modelling are underrepresented. Modelling can be seen as normative, when models are not only used to describe reality, but value or even generate reality, such as mathematical models used to assign legitimate carbon footprints within climate change discussion. Normative modelling for the political discourse requires reflecting about assumptions, simplifications and relevant consequences coming with the models. Starting from the well-known modelling cycle we integrate civic education perspectives to develop a didactical framework around normative modelling, suggesting an enhanced normative modelling cycle that explicitly refers to the judgement formation.

(Normative) mathematical modelling

Mathematical modelling is an important part of mathematics. A mathematical model is a simplified representation of reality that takes into account only certain aspects that can be sufficiently objectified and to which mathematical methods can be applied in order to obtain mathematical results. Models are not unambiguous, because it is possible to make simplifications in different ways. Thus, models should not be considered right or wrong, but more or less useful. The usefulness of a model can only be assessed with regard to the problem to be worked on (Greefrath et al., 2013).

Modelling may have different purposes, pending on the intended use of the model. For example, descriptive modelling mainly obtains to describe reality, such as physical relations e.g. the planetary orbits. At the same time we may use modelling to “specify or design objects or structures that are meant to inhabit some extra-mathematical domain whilst possessing (if possible) certain required or desired properties” (Niss, 2015, p. 69). This is what we call normative modelling, when reality is not just described, but prescribed as well. Common questions that would indicate normative modelling could be: “Where should a new power plant or a huge shopping centre be located? In what way should seats be apportioned amongst parties in parliamentary elections?” (ibid.). It is clear that normative modelling requires taking a stance that values certain qualities of a solution differently. Unlike many modelling problems in mathematics education, normative modelling cannot be validated.

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A recent and significant example for the relevance of normative modelling is climate change. It is one of the most striking problems that people and governments across the world are facing and it heavily relies on mathematical models both to understand the problem and to evaluate possible solutions. This issue has the potential to change the social and political order of the world (Beck, 2015, p. 75). The introduction of a CO₂ tax or global CO₂ quotas, the orientation towards the 1.5-degree target or the calculation of ecological footprints are only a few examples of themes, that are widely discussed within politics and society involving mathematical models.

The political dimension of normative modelling

Normative modelling is not only a special kind of modelling but it takes on an important role for political decision-making processes. The application of mathematical models for political decisions is hence in need for reflection. Central, for example, is the understanding that political judgements can never be obtained by calculation alone and that political actors can deliberately influence outcomes by making different assumptions. This brings mathematics education into the focus of education processes for democratic competences, especially for critical analysis skills. It is therefore of democratic importance, both from an individual and a societal perspective, to provide citizens with the competences to understand the role of mathematics in complex situations, such as climate change. In this context, “the purpose of mathematics education should be to enable students to realise, understand, judge, utilise and also perform the application of mathematics in society” (Niss, 1983, p. 248). This includes the application of models for political decision-making, but also the reflection on the principles and assumptions that shape the transformation of societal issues into mathematic models. We build on the principles of civic education aimed at providing competences for the critical reflection of democratic processes as well as the principles of a critical mathematics education. Our goal is not only to focus on normative models as an example for conjunction of political and mathematical processes, but also provide approaches to enable learners to critically reflect on said assumptions (Reinhardt, 2013, p. 101; Skovsmose, 1994, p. 58).

Teaching (normative) mathematical modelling

Mathematical modelling has found its way into (German) schools due to different aspects – but not in terms of normative modelling. The curricula focus on descriptive modelling, promoting real world applications of mathematics in problem solving and modelling (Kultusministerkonferenz, 2015). A very popular model used for teaching mathematical modelling is the modelling cycle. It can be used to illustrate the concept of modelling, taken as an aid for learners in the process of modelling, as well as diagnostic tool and basis for empirical studies (Greefrath et al., 2013). The modelling cycle involves seven steps to model a situation, which are displayed in blue in Figure 1 (see Greefrath et al., 2013, for further explanations).

Taking a closer look on steps two and three, the differences between normative and descriptive modelling become clear: For all modelling processes, the simplifications made in these steps, determine the results. However, in normative modelling, the results may have a

political dimension that should be discussed. We can only critically reflect on the results, when we take the assumptions for the model into account. This suggests that the sub-processes of the modelling cycle may not be able to fully capture what happens in evaluating models arising from normative modelling (Niss, 2015, pp. 69–77). We thus aim for an enhanced modelling cycle starting with the following points: Normative modelling requires more, namely political analysis of the situation (in addition to mathematical analysis), discussion of political possibilities, and judgment formation as subsequent steps. At a minimum, the discussion of political possibilities requires that different possibilities emerge from the mathematical models or that they be considered from the very beginning. Political analysis also requires identifying interests of involved stakeholders.

Figure 1: Our purpose of an adjusted normative modelling cycle

Developing an adjusted modelling

The modelling cycle provides indications of the steps in which alternatives and interests might be found. Understanding/Constructing (1.) at least does not involve conscious steps, but suggests that in normative modelling we may need to reconcile different conceptions of reality if we are to negotiate solutions in our societies. Simplifying (2.) is one of the most relevant steps. Which parts of the situation model are included at all and how interrelationships are simplified essentially determines the result. Here, alternatives have to be considered, their consequences for the model have to be estimated and they have to be classified with

regard to political interests. Mathematization (3.) is in itself a technical step, provided that the real model is specified precisely enough. In practice, however, the real model is specified more concretely in this step, so that simplifications similar to those in (2.) are to be expected here as well. The mathematical work (4.) will rarely provide starting points for the political discussion. Although alternative actions exist here (e.g., obtaining solutions algebraically or numerically), the differences, if any, should be irrelevant. Interpreting (5.) should also be more of a technical step because it initially involves only the translation of mathematical variables, functions, etc. into reality. However, generalizations could be made at this step, concerning e.g. model assumptions or restrictions of variable ranges, etc. Moreover, the presentation of the results will very often suggest actions, at least implicitly. Such (normative) statements can never be the result of a mathematical calculation and should therefore always be outsourced to the further steps. First, the different possibilities and the different implications related to the stakeholders' interests should be noted through the reflection and critique of the modelling just described. We named that to build a "map of possibilities". After that, everyone should form their own judgment (8.) by weighing the interests. Finally, we should acknowledge that our decision might have an impact on the world as we assume at this moment (relating to our situation model; 9.) and as it is (reality; 10.).

In relation to climate change, the normative modeling cycle could be used, for example, to teach about different ways of intervening to reduce CO₂ emissions. One possibility discussed is that of the meat tax or, more generally, the question of the CO₂ emission of various foods that are, for example, transported a long way or are expensive to grow or cultivate (1). Based on these individual situation models (2), a model could be set up in which different foods are each assigned a specific CO₂ emission for the production process (3). For the transformation into a mathematical model, relevant categories have to be identified and defined to describe the CO₂ emission of different foods. Among others, production, transport and the consequences of land use come into question here. In the simplest mathematical model, mean values per kilogram of the foodstuff are researched and summed up for these categories (4). The mathematical result is an overview of the total CO₂ emission for one kilogram of the respective food. The result would show that beef on pure meat herds has a relatively high CO₂ emission according to this model, as well as chocolate. In contrast, rice and tomatoes for example, have a significantly lower one (5). Scaling to 1000 kilocalories per food instead of kilograms would show a slightly different result: tomatoes would actually show higher CO₂ emissions than chocolate (Ritchie & Roser, 2020; Poore & Nemecek, 2018). It could also be discussed whether the preparation and composition (e.g. sugar vs. protein) of the food should be considered in further models (6). The various results could then be the starting point for a discussion, for example, on a meat tax and the associated effects, for example, of an economic or social nature (7). Students may take up different roles and may discuss who would be using which mathematical model to build argumentations and why. Following this, the students may develop a reasoned judgment about the best possible solution to the problem from their perspective and to reflect on the associated effects on the original real model (8). The judgment and the associated decision can then serve as a starting

point for a new situation model (9) or guide the students' own political action outside the classroom (10).

Outlook

In July 2021, the first teaching materials on CO₂ emissions from food as well as insect populations will be deployed and evaluated in a school context. First explorative results on student conceptions in the context of normative modelling will be collected. We hope to be able to discuss these with the scientific community, as well as our presented theoretical framework for normative modelling.

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